

The Hermitage of Sheikh Abd el-Qurna

Secondary source

Entered by Alexandra Konstantinidou

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Hermits, Christian, Religious Group, Egypt, Monasticism, Early Christian Monasticism in Egypt, Indo-European, Language, Religious Place, Afro-Asiatic

On the southern side of the so-called Third Valley (also known as the Valley of the Last Mentuhotep), high on the slopes of an unnamed hill, behind Sheikh Abd el-Qurna, an unfinished mortuary complex of Amenemhat Sehetepibre is located. It includes two tombs, TT 1151 and TT 1152, which were occupied by two Christian hermits, in the last decades of the fifth century. The tombs were used by subsequent generations of monks, until their eventual abandonment in the eighth century. It is demonstrated that Tomb TT 1152 was prepared for one of the court officials of the Middle Kingdom in Thebes and it is dated to the end of the Eleventh or the beginning of the Twelfth Dynasty. Whereas it was never finished, certain parts of its interior, such as the entrance corridor and the cult chapel were completed. It was repetitively used for sepulchral purposes between the Second Intermediate Period and the beginning of the Late Period. In front of the entrance to the tomb there was an open courtyard, which would have been normally surrounded by a mud-brick wall; however, this wall was never built. In the centre of the rock facade there was the entrance to the tomb leading to a long rock-cut corridor with a square chamber at the end – the funerary cult chapel. In the floor of this chamber, there was an entrance to a deep shaft. Usually, at the bottom of this shaft, there was another corridor leading to the burial chamber. In TT 1152, the burial chamber was never hewn, as work stopped during the preparation of the corridor. The monks who occupied the tomb made certain adjustments. They added benches and a 'bed', and they decorated the rock walls with crosses, two figures of equestrian saints, Christ and inscriptions using red and yellow colours. At a later stage, in the courtyard in front of the tomb, domestic and industrial facilities as well as an almost 6-metres high mud-brick defensive tower/ keep were constructed. Access to the tower was possible through an upper-floor chamber that was reached using a ladder from the outside. Thus, it appears that the area outside the hermitage served economic purposes (e.g. craft activities, storage of raw materials for production, preparation of meals). The character of the front part of the interior was rather sacral (place of prayer), but it was also a reception area. The hermitage was probably occupied by two monks, a master and his disciple, who manufactured textiles, baskets and leather artefacts. TT 1151 is located 40m north of TT 1152. There, the alterations performed by the monks included plastering of the rock walls and floor covering. In the entrance of the corridor a pavement running 14m was laid. Most of it was a hard lime mortar and some sections at the back were of tamped clay. Just inside the entrance, the floor was composed of small limestone slabs imitating gray-white marble, decorated with a large cross whose outlines were marked with regular pieces of red-brick tiles. The mud plaster coating of the walls was decorated with elaborate geometric motifs, intersecting circles, crosses and inscriptions. Two low masonry benches, separated by a low mud-brick wall, were attached to the eastern wall of the corridor. TT 1151 was used as a place for prayer and worship instead of habitation. Three manuscripts were retrieved from the rubbish dump. These are very important and rare finds. Two of these manuscripts were books written on papyrus and bound in leather, the covers blind-tooled and decorated. One contained the Canons of Pseudo-Basil and is provisionally dated to the seventh/ eighth century. It is the only full text of these canons in the Coptic language (Sahidic dialect). The cover of the second codex is decorated with a red-painted Chi-Ro sign inside a circle and a guilloche. This book was an Enkomion of St Pisenhios, bishop of Keft (Koptos), who lived in AD 568–632. The third book was a series of 51 loose parchment cards placed among two wooden boards pasted with thin leather. One card bears a text in Greek that is dated to the eighth century. Two others, presumed to be palimpsests, contained passages from chapters 35 and 36 of the apocryphal Acts of

St. Peter recounting the martyrdom of the saint. The remaining 48 cards contained some of the final chapters of the Old Testament Book of Isaiah.

Date Range: 480 CE - 750 CE

Region: Sheikh Abd el-Qurna

Region tags: Africa, Egypt, Egyptian Desert, North Africa

Sheikh Abd el-Qurna

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation
– Hill

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure
– No

↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: No

↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

↳ A group of features:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes
Notes: Monasticism of Western Thebes.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Individual

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes
Notes: Middle Kingdom tomb (TT 1152) transformed into a hermitage.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
– Other [specify]: Abandoned, natural decay, modern robbing.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
– Other [specify]: No

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Other [specify]: No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God/ Christ

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Górecki, T. 2013. Archaeological excavation in the Coptic hermitage at Gurna (Egypt). The research program, the particulars of the research and initial findings. In M. Dolińska, T. Górecki, A. Reiche, and A. Twardecki (eds) *The Collection of Ancient and East Christian Art and Archaeological Excavation of the National Museum in Warsaw* (=Rocznik Muzeum Narodowego w Warszawie 32): 34-39; 49-51. Warsaw.
- Source 2: Górecki, T. 2013. The hermitage in Sheikh Abd el-Gurna (West Thebes). Excavation, studies and conservation in 2009 and 2010/2011. *Polish Archaeology in the Mediterranean* 22: 171-192.
- Source 3: Chudzik, P. 2013. Preliminary remarks on the architecture of the Theban Tomb 1152 at Sheikh Abd el-Gurna. *Polish Archaeology in the Mediterranean* 22: 193-198.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Terracing

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://pcma.uw.edu.pl/en/2019/01/31/sheikh-abd-el-gurna-2/>
- Source 1 Description: Polish Centre of Mediterranean Archaeology, University of Warsaw: Sheikh Abd el-

Qurna

– Source 2 URL: <http://archo.edu.pl/misjaeremu/index.htm>

– Source 2 Description: Misja Eremu

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2003-2016

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Polish Archaeological Mission at Sheikh Abd el-Qurna (Hermitage in Tombs MMA 1151 and 1152)

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: It is situated in the desert.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: Ostraca, papyri and manuscripts have been discovered. They were used by the individuals that lived in the hermitage.

Sources and Excavations

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Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

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– Yes

Type of feature

– Terracing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

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Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: It is situated in the desert.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

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Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

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Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

One single feature

– Other [specify]: No

A group of structures:

– Yes

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

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↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

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Notes: Monasticism of Western Thebes.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

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↳ Worship:

– Individual

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

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↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

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–Other [specify]: Abandoned, natural decay, modern robbing.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God/ Christ

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

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Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

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– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

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Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Notes: Ostraca, papyri and manuscripts have been discovered. They were used by the individuals that lived in the hermitage.

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

- Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

- Yes

↳ On the outside:

- No

↳ On the inside:

- Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

- No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

- Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

- Yes

Notes: Christ, equestrian saints

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

- No

- ↳ Are there humans depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Are there animals depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - Yes
 - ↳ Floral motifs
 - No
 - ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - No
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Crosses
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
 - No
- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

 - No
- ↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– Other [specify]: I don't know

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Christ, equestrian saints

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– I don't know

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– I don't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Hill.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– I don't know

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Hill.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

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– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

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↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

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↳ Are there gods depicted:

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Notes: Christ, equestrian saints

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–Other [specify]: Crosses

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↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– I don't know

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– I don't know

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: No

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:
– No

Are pilgrimages present:
– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– I don't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– I don't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– I don't know

Is divination present:
– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: A hermitage was established in a Middle Kingdom tomb.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– I don't know

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Liturgy, prayer

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– I don't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: A hermitage was established in a Middle Kingdom tomb.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

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Are grave goods present:

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Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

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↳ Are they sky deity:

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↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

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Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

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Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– I don't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– I don't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– I don't know

Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Hermits

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– I don't know

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Hermits

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No